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HOW TO THINK IN ENGLISH?

Khasanova Qunduzkhon

Student, Urgench state university, Foreign Philology faculty

Today English has become a global language. This language is recognized as an official or second main language of many countries. English is used in many international conferences, meetings, sports competitions and a number of other processes around the world. The Internet, which is constantly used by almost everyone and has become an integral part of human life, is also in English. For this reason, an in-depth and thorough study of this international language is essential for almost all professionals, and many countries are beginning to teach English to children as a foreign language from school age. Also in our country, in Uzbekistan, the emphasis on teaching English is enormous, and this language is taught to children from kindergarten to high school.

However, no goal or dream in our lives is easy to achieve, and you may also face some challenges in learning foreign languages perfectly. There is a saying among our people, "Think first, then speak." This proverb is not uttered in vain, it is natural for people to think about what they want to talk about first. When we speak in our native language or communicate with someone, we automatically think of the sentences we want to say in our brains and quickly articulate them verbally. It is very easy for us. But what about when we speak a foreign language? A lot of learners are much better at expressive reading, fluent writing and listening comprehension in English, but unfortunately when it comes to speaking, they have a bit of a hard time. Why? The answer to this question is very simple because they do not know how to think in English. When many language learners try to speak a foreign language, they begin to translate the ideas one by one in the brain, and the process takes a long time. As a result, in a sentence that can be spoken in 5 minutes, they can spend about 10 minutes and often complain that they cannot speak English as fast and fluently as their mother tongue. That is why, we should not translate our thoughts one by one, not only in English, but also in any foreign language. We just need to know how to think in that language.

But how can we learn to think in English? There are a variety of ways to do this proven by specialized linguists, teachers, and some people interested in learning languages. First of all, if you want to speak English beautifully and quickly, and be able to think automatically, you need to have enough vocabulary. Because memorizing new words and putting them

into practice is the key to learning every new language. Imagine, you are sitting in a room and there are all sorts of objects around you. If you have memorized the words about home appliances, you will quickly start thinking about the names of the things around you in English and you will be able to speak fluently on this topic in the future. This exercise is very useful and effective. Secondly, when you do something, such as cooking, cleaning, doing laundry, traveling, whatever you do, you have to think of those actions' names in English, such as “ I'm cleaning ”, " I am studying ". The next great and fun way to boost your ability to think in English is to read art books. Unfortunately, some learners find this path a bit boring and can not find enough patience in themselves to read English novels and stories. Admittedly, this is a very sad situation. Since fiction books undoubtedly play a necessary role in learning to think in a foreign language. If you read a fiction novel and find it very interesting for yourself, no doubt you will start thinking about the events in the work, the characters in it, what they said in the language in which the book was written, and they will not leave your mind. Another way to develop thinking in English is to watch foreign movies, series and talk shows. If fiction is a very boring process for you, watching modern and engaging movies can also be a very helpful way in learning to think in a foreign language. Nowadays we have numerous films and television shows in order to improve your target language, such as Harry Potter, Friends, The Tonight Show, The Late Late Show, The Ellen DeGeneres Show and so on. As all of them are extremely interesting and funny, you will never be bored while learning languages. These programs use colourful words, collocations, phrasal verbs and sentences which are exceedingly practical for your speech. Provided that you watch them every single day, your English will be better and better. In today's world, this is not problem to watch such kind of shows anywhere thanks to technological developments like cell phones, computers and tablets. In spite of the fact that you are going to somewhere, you can easily access to the Internet to watch your favourite TV show with your mobile phone without any difficulties. So we have so many opportunities to learn any language and think in the language.